

Data management plan for PG-0036 project

Version 1

Description

Data Management Plan (DMPs) are a key element of good data management. This document presents the plan for managing data and other outputs of the Recovery and Resilience Mechanism Post doctoral call for proposals 2024 "Sustainable cooling technologies for affordable thermal comfort in buildings".

It aims to provide guidance on the management of data throughout the entire project lifetime and beyond by setting guidelines and recommendations on how data should be made

available in a manner that is findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable (FAIR):

- the handling of research data during & after the end of the project
- what data will be collected, processed and/or generated
- which methodology & standards will be applied
- whether data will be shared/made open access and
- how data will be curated & preserved (including after the end of the project).

The DMP has been created in accordance with the Latvian Open Science Strategy 2021-2027, Chapter 4 "Action Plan for the Latvian Open Science Strategy 2021 - 2027", point 2. The DMP is a key element of good data management and describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected during the project, processed and/or generated by

project. The establishment of the DMP is the deliverable of WP1 – Project planning and dissemination. The purpose of the DMP is to provide an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy for all datasets that will be generated by the project.

The DMP will be a living document, continuously updated to facilitate the management of project data and outputs. The final version will summarize all the data during the whole duration of the project.

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

PG-0036

Researchers

Arturs Brahmanis (0009-0003-0301-3384)

Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Data management plan for PG-0036 project](#)

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: PG-0036

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Restricted

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

LCS FARP

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of collection of the data in this study is to determine the optimality of parameters of the HVAC system, and level of satisfaction with indoor comfort.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Survey data
- Aggregate data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- CSV
- PNG
- XLS
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

300

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Will be considered during the study

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

To the other scientists doing research on HVAC, and human thermal comfort

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS EXCEL or similar

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Costs will be covered from the project funding

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

PG-0036

The grant manager will be responsible for data management

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

After the realization of the project FAIR costs will be Covered by institution

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall

- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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